

The logo for DCMi 2023 features a stylized orange sunburst icon to the left of the text "DCMI 2023". The "DCMI" is in orange and "2023" is in grey.

DCMI 2023

Metadata Innovation:

Enabling Knowledge in a Data-Intensive World

2023 **November 6** ^{Mon} - **November 9** ^{Thu}
Global Plaza, Kyungpook National University

The Dublin Core logo, featuring a stylized orange sunburst icon.

Dublin Core

The logo for Kyungpook National University, featuring a circular emblem with a book and a lamp.

BK21 KYUNGPOOK NATIONAL UNIVERSITY
Dept. of Library & Information Science

Greetings

Welcome to the 2023 DCMI Conference: “Metadata Innovation - Enabling Knowledge in a Data-Intensive World.”

The Dublin Core community stands at the forefront, championing metadata interoperability by harnessing the power of cutting-edge IT solutions. I am delighted to extend a warm welcome to all attendees of this pivotal conference.

Our agenda features three riveting keynotes that are intimately aligned with the latest developments in both our societal and IT landscapes. We commence with a keynote on “Unleashing the Synergy between Dublin Core and AI,” delivered by Professor Emeritus Sunghyon Mayeng from KAIST. This will be followed by an insightful session on “Maintaining Metadata Simplicity in Complex Settings” by Niklas Lindstrom from the Sweden National Library. An eminent practitioner and engineer in the field, Lindstrom’s expertise promises an enlightening presentation. Concluding the keynote series, Javed Dean and Professor Mostafa from the University of Toronto’s Faculty of Information will delve into the nuances of “Health Data Exchange.”

Beyond these keynotes, our conference boasts an impressive lineup of invited panels, talks, academic papers, tutorials, workshops, best practice showcases, a student forum, and essential community updates.

We would like to extend our deepest gratitude to Kyungpook National University’s Department of Library and Information Science BK21 for graciously hosting the DCMI 2023 Conference. Additionally, our heartfelt thanks go out to our sponsors: Korea Tourism Organization, Daegu Convention Bureau, and Taxonomy Strategies. Your support and collaboration have been invaluable.

We are confident that your participation in this conference will prove immensely valuable. We eagerly await your presence at the DCMI 2023 Annual Conference!

Sam Oh

Executive Director, Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
Distinguished Professor for Global Affairs, Sungkyunkwan University

Greetings

It is with immense pleasure and honor that I extend a warm welcome to each and every one of you to the DCMI Conference 2023, hosted at Kyungpook National University(KNU) in the beautiful city of Daegu, Korea. As the Chair of this remarkable event, I am thrilled to have the opportunity to bring together experts and enthusiasts from around the world in this vibrant location renowned for its rich history and technological innovation.

Over the next few days, we have an exciting agenda planned, carefully crafted to provide you with a stimulating and immersive experience. Our esteemed speakers, drawn from diverse backgrounds and areas of expertise, will deliver thought-provoking keynote addresses, shedding light on the latest advancements and real-world applications of metadata. The conference program is further enriched with interactive workshops, engaging panel discussions, and enlightening paper presentations, all designed to foster collaborative learning and innovative thinking.

As we gather here at KNU, we acknowledge the invaluable support and contributions from the organizing committee, sponsors, and dedicated volunteers who have worked tirelessly to ensure the success of this conference. Their commitment and hard work are truly commendable, and we owe them our sincere appreciation.

To our esteemed participants, I encourage you to seize this opportunity to actively engage in the conference activities. Take advantage of the networking sessions, forge new connections, and share your valuable insights. The power of metadata lies not only in its theoretical foundations but also in the collective knowledge and experiences we bring to the table. Let us leverage this platform to exchange ideas, discuss emerging trends, and forge collaborations that will shape the future of metadata practices.

Once again, I extend my warmest welcome to the DCMI Conference 2023 at KNU, Daegu, Korea. May this conference be a transformative experience that broadens our horizons, deepens our understanding, and paves the way for a future where metadata continues to empower data integration and discovery.

Thank you, and enjoy the conference!

Heesop Kim

Conference Chair
Professor (iSchool, Kyungpook National University)

Day 1 / 11. 6. (Mon) / 09:00~20:00

Time	Title	
08:00 ~ 09:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Registration	
Session 1	Welcome • Moderator: Kyong Eun Oh	
09:00 ~ 09:30 Gyeongha Hall 1	Heesop Kim (Kyungpook National University)	Welcome Address
Session 2	Keynote 1: Synergy between Dublin Core and AI • Moderator: Sam Oh	
09:30 ~ 10:30 Gyeongha Hall 1	Sung-Hyon Myaeng (KAIST)	Unleashing the synergy between Dublin Core and AI : Enriching Metadata and Enhancing AI Training
10:30 ~ 11:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Coffee Break	
Session 3	Invited Talk 1: Metadata in the Age of AI • Moderator: Sam Oh	
11:00 ~ 12:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Tom Baker (DCMI)	Properties, Classes, Concepts, Shapes, Vectors : Metadata in the Age of AI
Session 4	Invited Talk 2: Decolonization and Metadata • Moderator: Hussein Suleman	
12:00 ~ 13:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Stacy Allison-Cassin (Dalhousie University)	Listening, Learning, and Change: Decolonization and Metadata
13:00 ~ 14:30 BIBIM-GA	Lunch	
Session 5	Papers 1: Metadata and Scholarly Communications • Moderator: Alasdair MacDonald	
14:30 ~ 16:00 Room 201	Julianna Pakstis (Children's Hospital of Philadelphia)	Research Data Description From Structures Within and Around Metadata
	Nishad Thalath (University of Tsukuba)	Sustainable Scholarly Publishing: Insights and Lessons from DCPapers
	Chai Miaoling (Chengdu Library and Information Center)	Research on the Method of Linking Scientific Data and Literature Data through Metadata Fusion and Ontology Construction
	Frédéric Piedboeuf (University of Montreal)	The state of OAI-PMH repositories in Canadian Universities
Session 6	Panel 1: BIBFRAME and Beyond	
16:00 ~ 17:30 Room 201	Niklas Lindström (National Library of Sweden) Philip Schreur (Stanford University) Xiaoli Li (University of California Davis Library)	BIBFRAME and Beyond: On data resilience, effective interoperability, knowledge sharing and the future of linked library data
17:30 ~ 18:00 SKY 17	Poster Display	
18:00 ~ 20:00 SKY 17	Social Dinner	

Day 2 / 11. 7. (Tue) / 09:00~18:00

Time	Title	
08:00 ~ 09:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Registration	
Session 8	Keynote 2: Maintaining Metadata Simplicity • Moderator: Tom Baker	
09:00 ~ 10:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Niklas Lindström (National Library of Sweden)	Maintaining Metadata Simplicity in Complex Settings
10:00 ~ 10:30 Gyeongha Hall 1	Coffee Break	
Session 9	Panel 2: The Evolving Roots of Discovery	
10:30 ~ 12:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Peter Broadwell (Stanford University Libraries) Peter Leonard (Stanford Libraries) Philip Schreur (Stanford University) Tom Cramer (Stanford University) Simeon Warner (Cornell University)	The Evolving Roots of Discovery : New Models of Metadata Creation, Collection, and Reuse
Session 10	Invited Talk 3: Complexities of Archival Metadata • Moderator: Jian Qin	
12:00 ~ 13:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Anne J. Gilliland (Department of Information Studies, UCLA)	Questions of Age, Questions of Evidence: Contemplating the Complexities of Archival Metadata for Historical Korean and Korean American Materials
13:00 ~ 14:30 BIBIM-GA	Lunch	
Session 11	Panel 3: The Use of Metadata by Artificial Intelligence	
14:30 ~ 16:00 Room 201	Artem Reshetnikov (Barcelona Supercomputing Center)	How does metadata contribute to the reinforcement of human stereotypes in AI systems?
	Craig Eby (Cogniva Information Solutions)	Harnessing Metadata for AI Systems
Session 12	Invited Talk 4: Open Science and Open Metadata • Moderator: Inkyung Choi	
16:00 ~ 17:00 Room 201	Rochelle Lundy (Stanford University) Tom Cramer (Stanford University)	OSTP, Open Science, and Open Metadata : The impact of changing U.S. public access mandates
Session 13	Recent Innovations: Short Papers and Posters • Moderator: Jian Qin	
16:00 ~ 17:00 Room 203	Jian Qin (Syracuse University) Bei Yu (Syracuse University)	Metadata in Trustworthy AI: From Data Quality to ML Modeling
	Robin Dresel (National Library Board)	Designing a Linked Data Service across borders and timezones : the National Library Board's experience
	Xiaoli Li (University of California Davis Library)	BIBFRAME Interoperability Group One Year Update
	Robert J. Rovetto (Independent and student)	The Ethics of Metadata
Session 14	Invited Talk 5: How Metadata Can Reduce Digital Waste • Moderator: Gema Bueno de la Fuente	

16:00 ~ 17:00 Room 209	Gerry McGovern	How metadata can reduce digital waste
Session 15	DCMI Community Updates	• Moderator: Alasdair MacDonald
17:00 ~ 18:00 Room 201	DCMI Community Updates	

Day 3 / 11.8. (Wed) / 09:00~19:00

Time	Title
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08:00 ~ 09:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Registration
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Session 16	Keynote 3: Health Data Exchange (HDX)	• Moderator: Sam Oh
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09:00 ~ 10:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Javed Mostafa (Dean and Professor, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto)	Health Data Exchange (HDX): A global open data, software, and learning-community resource for R&D acceleration and dissemination
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Session 17	Student Forum	• Moderator: Ying-Hsang Liu
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09:15 ~ 11:30 KNU Library	In person	B.M. Watson (University of British Columbia)	The Trans Metadata Collective
		Inyoung Jung (Kyungpook National University)	A Preliminary Study on Interlinking Metadata Elements for the Official Documents of the Japanese Government General of Korea
	Online	Hannah Moutran (University of Texas at Austin) Hannah Moutran, Rachel Deitch (University of Texas at Austin)	Linked Metadata for Nazi Looted Art
		Whitney Nelson, Sam Curtis (School of Information, University of Texas)	When Nightwing and Superman Crossover : Knowledge Graphs & Comics
		Heather Wiegert (University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign) Katie Colson (Stanford University)	Makerspace Metadata Schema Implementation : Manual Deduplication Efforts in a Learning Object Repository
		Hugh Paterson III (University of North Texas)	Considering WEMI and the Digital Artifacts Around Language Documentation Transcripts
		Morgan Adle (University of Maryland)	Metadata Quality : Manual Deduplication Efforts in a Learning Object Repository

10:00 ~ 10:30 Gyeongha Hall 1	Coffee Break	
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Session 18	Panel 4: Metadata Creation, Discovery, and AI Applications	• Moderator: Jian Qin
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10:30 ~ 12:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Shu-Jiun (Sophy) Chen (Academia Sinica Center for Digital Culture)	Knowledge Organization in Digital Humanities Research : A Case Study of Archives of Qing Secret Societies
	Haiqing Lin (C.V. Starr East Asian Library, UC Berkeley)	Towards AI/ML-Friendly Metadata : A Metadata Architecture for Effective AI/ML Dataset Management
	Jian Qin (Syracuse University)	Metadata and Trustworthy AI

Session 19	Invited Talk 6: LLM to Annotate Subject Metadata	• Moderator: Sam Oh
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12:00 ~ 13:00 Gyeongha Hall 1	Shiwei Zhang (RMIT University)	Utilising a Large Language Model to Annotate Subject Metadata : A Case Study with an Australia National Research Data Catalogue
13:00 ~ 14:30 BIBIM-GA	Lunch	
Session 20	Panel 5: Solutions for Interdisciplinary Data Integration	
14:30 ~ 16:00 Room 201	Laura Molloy (CODATA) Arofan Gregory (CODATA) Simon Hodson (CODATA)	Envisioning Solutions for Interdisciplinary Data Integration : the Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)
Session 21	Papers 2: Metadata Management and Perspectives • Moderator: Joseph Busch	
16:00 ~ 17:30 Room 201	Kemi Olayemi (Main Library, Bayero University Kano)	The Mediating Role of Librarians' Competencies in the Application of Metadata Practices for the Management of Digital Information Resources in University Libraries in Nigeria
	Karen M Wickett (University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign)	Metadata as a Site for Critical Inquiry
	Yong-Sang Cho (Open Cyber University of Korea)	ISO/IEC 19788-1: A metadata framework
	Marina Salse (Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media, University of Barcelona)	Library and Information Science students and DCMI Metadata Terms : do they understand the resource?
Session 22	Closing ceremony • Moderator: Sam Oh	
17:30 ~ 17:40 Room 201	Closing ceremony	
17:40 ~ 19:00 Room 201	DCMI Governing Board Meeting	
Day 4 / 11. 9. (Thu) / 09:00~18:00		
Time	Title	
08:00 ~ 09:00 Room 201	Registration	
Session 23	Tutorial 1: LLMs for Semantic Web Query • Moderator: Inkyung Choi	
09:00 ~ 10:30 Room 209	Yinlin Chen (Virginia Tech University Libraries)	LLMs for Semantic Web Query
Session 24	Tutorial 2: Prompt Engineering and Metadata	
09:00 ~ 12:30 Room 201	Jian Qin (Syracuse University) Bei Yu (Syracuse University)	Prompt Engineering and Metadata
Session 25	NKOS Workshop * 4:45-20:00 Online Only • Moderator: Joseph Busch	
09:00 ~ 20:15 Room 309	NKOS Workshop * 4:45-20:00 Online Only	
10:30 ~ 11:00 Room 201	Coffee Break	

Session 26		Tutorial 3: Metadata Maker	• Moderator: Inkyung Choi
11:00 ~ 12:30 Room 209	<p>Myung-Ja Han (University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign)</p> <p>Greta Heng (San Diego State University)</p> <p>Patricia Lampron (University of California Irvine)</p>	<p>Metadata Maker</p> <p>: a Simple Editor that Creates MARC to Linked Data</p>	
12:30 ~ 14:00 BIBIM-GA	Lunch		
Session 27		Best Practice	• Moderator: Eun Youp Rha, Jongwook Lee
14:00 ~ 18:00 Best Practice Room 201	<p>Shu-Jiun (Sophy) Chen (Academia Sinica Center for Digital Culture)</p>	<p>Datafication in Qing Dynasty Archives and Digital Humanities</p> <p>: A case study of the State Investigations of Popular Religious Sects</p>	
	<p>Jiao Li (Agricultural Information Institute of CAAS)</p>	<p>A hybrid approach for data-literature linking</p>	
	<p>Joseph Busch (Taxonomy Strategies)</p>	<p>African Development Bank SANKOFA Programme</p>	
	<p>Myung-Ja (MJ) Han (University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign)</p> <p>Greta Heng (San Diego State University)</p> <p>Patricia Lampron (University of California Irvine)</p>	<p>Towards Linked data Creation in Integrated Library System</p>	
	<p>Matthias Kaun (Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin Berlin State Library)</p>	<p>Data management and services in the context of CrossAsia - between strategy and pragmatism</p>	
	<p>Antoine Isaac (Europeana Foundation)</p>	<p>Towards a methodology for validation of metadata enrichments in Europeana</p>	
	<p>Yūko MURAO (National Diet Library, Japan)</p> <p>HIRATA Noriko (National Diet Library, Japan)</p>	<p>Guidelines for Metadata Distribution in Japan</p> <p>: Improving Interoperability of Metadata to Digital Resources</p>	
	<p>Francisco Carlos Paletta (University of São Paulo)</p>	<p>Metadata Principles, Guidelines and Best Practices: A Case Study of Brazil and Sri Lanka</p>	
	<p>Eleftheria Tsoupra (Europeana Foundation)</p>	<p>Identifying and reporting data quality problems in Europeana</p>	
	<p>Yeonhee Park (Korean Education and Research Information Service)</p>	<p>Korean Academic shared cataloging and linking beyond</p>	
<p>Cuijuan Xia (Shanghai Library)</p>	<p>Design an Ontology AP of Ancient Chinese Inscription Rubbings for Cultural transmission and Art Appreciation</p>		
Session 28		IIF Workshop	
14:00 ~ 18:00 Workshop Room 209	<p>Tom Cramer (Stanford University)</p> <p>Simeon Warner (Cornell University)</p>	<p>IIF(International Image Interoperability Framework)</p>	
15:30 ~ 16:00 Room 201	Coffee Break		
Closing			